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Examination of Postural Orthostatic Tachycardia Syndrome: Links With COVID-19 and Effects on Patients Physically and Mentally

Postural Orthostatic Tachycardia Syndrome is an autonomic condition that causes dizziness and lightheadedness, fatigue, migraines, and brain fog upon standing up or doing physical activities. POTS has been affecting many people in the world, with few people knowing about the research found surrounding POTS. POTS affects up to 3,000,000 people in the United States with 1/3 of those people being under the age of 18 (Boris 2018). This condition is important for people to know and learn for adults, children, and parents everywhere. Despite POTS being very common, there are likely more people with POTS than we know. Many people with POTS are misdiagnosed or not diagnosed at all, with the average time for diagnosis is between 11 months and as long as 5 years (Dysautonomia International). This is extremely dangerous for people with POTS to not get diagnosed or wait multiple years for a diagnosis. During this time, people with POTS can suffer with extremely severe symptoms and not get the treatment they need. 25% of people with POTS are so disabled that they are physically unable to work (Boris 2018). Awareness and research for POTS must grow for recognition and diagnosis of POTS to be more accurate and effective. Because many people have symptoms of POTS without physiological issues being found and POTS symptoms being like many other diseases, confusion and difficulties diagnosing POTS are extremely high (Olshansky et al 2020). In this paper, the current body of knowledge about POTS being caused by COVID-19 and the difficulties of living with POTS and the diagnosis process will be discussed.

First, many people who had COVID-19 are getting or have already gotten POTS, with many still struggling for a diagnosis. A large portion of COVID-19 survivors have POTS within 6-8 months (Mallick et al 2023). Clearly, COVID-19 and POTS seem to be correlated, which could provide an area to understand POTS better, potentially improving treatment and diagnosis of POTS. Specifically, 2% - 14% of COVID-19 survivors develop POTS and 9%-61% develop POTS-like symptoms (Ormiston et al 2022). Because of this, more research needs to be done on the potential causes of this trend, and the bodily functions COVID-19 affects that may cause POTS. Despite limited knowledge of the causes, there can still be changes made because of this trend being clear. Testing for POTS as well as heart rate lowering medication needs to be ready for people who recently had COVID-19, which is resulting in a higher demand for autonomic specialists (Ormiston et al 2022). Although the cause of this is not completely known, largely because this is a very recent phenomenon, there are some speculative ideas that provide possible explanations. One reason for this is autoimmunity mechanisms that COVID-19 disrupts. Studies have found that COVID-19 antibodies cross react with components of neuronal and cardiovascular receptors which can disrupt the autonomic nervous system (Park et al 2022). Despite there being so much to still research and learn about this topic, findings like this help us to understand both COVID-19 and POTS better and could lead to further findings about POTS mechanisms and potential treatment for both COVID-19 and POTS. It should be noted that every

study, report, and article cited in this section noted this area to be understudied and in need of more research.

Secondly, people living with POTS struggle with severe symptoms, and because POTS can be difficult to diagnose, they deal with these symptoms without proper treatment. The struggle for diagnosis can also impact people living with POTS mentally. Doctors around the world need to be more educated on POTS and must find ways to speed up the diagnosis process, with many people with POTS feeling undeserved of healthcare and support provision (Knoop and Dunwoody, 2022). Because of these mental challenges, POTS can affect people in many more ways than just physically. This is an issue that is prevalent in POTS especially but is also seen in other chronic illnesses and diseases where people are told that their symptoms are just in their head or are just anxiety. Furthermore, long diagnosis processes result in many doctor visits, often with multiple different specialists, which is extremely expensive for someone who just wants to be treated for their symptoms. Living with POTS has financial burdens, and it also can have negative effects on family, work, and social relationships (Knoop and Dunwoody, 2022). Furthermore, the POTS diagnosis process can lead to patients feeling lost and hopeless. This is shown in a longitudinal study where the patients found little to no progress in their diagnosis over the span of six months (Knoop et al 2024). Another thing that this study found is that the process for patients getting their diagnosis is far from linear, which can increase frustration and confusion for patients. New-found problems throughout the process continued to be substantial (Knoop et al 2024). This sets patients further back in the process and adds to the complexity of their diagnosis. Patients were also interviewed in this study, and they shared why they wanted a diagnosis and what it would mean for them. These patients revealed that although they know they will still deal with POTS, they want the clarity that what they are feeling is real and they do not have to be guilty or blame themselves for their symptoms (Knoop et al 2024). A quote from one participant in this study encapsulates this feeling of wanting clarity perfectly:

I think it means, apart from the fact that I can stop feeling guilty about not being able to do stuff, or feeling sort of lazy, or stupid or, uncapable or anything like that. I know nothing is changing, and I'm still going to be tired and all of those sorts of things. But at least knowing there's a reason, and I don't just need to try harder, that there is actually something physically wrong, means I can stop blaming myself...So, the other, it's just everything is making sense. (Knoop et al 2024)

People living with POTS have been shown, in multiple different studies, to want a diagnosis of their symptoms to improve their mental health and feel progression throughout their POTS journey and their overall life.

In summary, people struggling with Postural Orthostatic Tachycardia Syndrome (POTS) have severe symptoms like dizziness and lightheadedness, fatigue, migraines, and brain fog when they stand up or do physical activity. Living with POTS can be very difficult even beyond the physical challenges because of mental struggles that come with dealing with POTS and working

towards a diagnosis. People who had COVID-19 are linked to later getting POTS, although the cause is not fully known or proven and needs to be further researched. It is difficult to get a POTS diagnosis because POTS can have similar symptoms to other diseases, and it is difficult for doctors to ensure that patients' symptoms are from POTS. Many of these issues root from POTS not being researched enough, because this causes a lack of understanding of POTS which negatively impacts patients who suffer from POTS. This includes patients struggling financially because of frequent doctor appointments during long diagnosis processes, losing bonds with family and friends, and also suffering financially because of POTS making it difficult for many people to work. Overall, POTS must be researched more for the well-being of people around the world with POTS. Further research could be focused on the reasons for COVID-19 being linked to POTS.

Works Cited

Boris, Jeffrey R. "Postural Orthostatic Tachycardia Syndrome in Children and Adolescents."

Autonomic Neuroscience, vol. 215, Dec. 2018, pp. 97-101,

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autneu.2018.05.004>.

Knoop, I., & Dunwoody, L. (2022). "You're always fighting": the lived experience of people with postural orthostatic tachycardia syndrome (POTS). *Disability and Rehabilitation*, 45(10),

1629–1635. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09638288.2022.2071482>

Knoop, Iris, et al. "One or Many Labels? A Longitudinal Qualitative Study of Patients' Journey to Diagnosis at a Specialist NHS Postural Tachycardia Syndrome (PoTS) Clinic." *PLOS ONE*, vol. 19, no. 7, 10 July 2024, p. e0302723,

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0302723>.

Mallick, Deobrat, et al. "COVID-19 Induced Postural Orthostatic Tachycardia Syndrome (POTS): A Review." *Cureus*, 31 Mar. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.36955>.

Olshansky, Brian, et al. "Postural Orthostatic Tachycardia Syndrome (POTS): A Critical Assessment." *Progress in Cardiovascular Diseases*, vol. 63, no. 3, May 2020, pp. 263-

70, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pcad.2020.03.010>.

Ormiston, Cameron K., et al. "Postural Orthostatic Tachycardia Syndrome as a Sequela of COVID-19." *Heart Rhythm*, vol. 19, no. 11, Nov. 2022, pp. 1880-89,

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrthm.2022.07.014>.

Park, J., Kim, S., Lee, J. *et al.* A case of transient POTS following COVID-19 vaccine. *Acta*

Neurol Belg **122**, 1081–1083 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13760-022-02002-2>

"10 Facts Doctors Should Know About POTS." *Dysautonomia International*,

dysautonomiainternational.org/page.php?ID=180.

